

Wearable health-tracking technologies in pregnancy: capabilities, clinical evidence, and implementation challenges

Afiyze Ahmedova¹,
Vesselina Yanachkova^{3,4}

1 Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University-Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

2 Faculty of Public Health, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

3 Research Institute, Medical University-Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

4 Specialized Hospital for Active Treatment of Obstetrics and Gynecology “Dr Shterev”, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Hristina Lebanova (hristina.lebanova@mu-pleven.bg)

Received 4 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 17 January 2026 ♦ Published 2 February 2026

Citation: Ahmedova A, Veleva N, Stoev S, Petkova-Gueorguieva E, Yanachkova V, Lebanova H (2026) Wearable health-tracking technologies in pregnancy: capabilities, clinical evidence, and implementation challenges. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e184239>

Abstract

Wearable health-tracking technologies are increasingly incorporated into prenatal care to enable continuous, noninvasive monitoring of maternal and fetal health. Devices such as smartwatches, fitness trackers, smart rings, and medical-grade biosensors can collect longitudinal data on physiological parameters, including heart rate, physical activity, sleep patterns, and pregnancy-specific indicators. When integrated with mobile health (mHealth) platforms and artificial intelligence (AI)-based analytics, these technologies offer opportunities for earlier identification of pregnancy-related complications and more personalized care. This narrative review summarizes current evidence on the application of wearable technologies during pregnancy, with a focus on monitoring capabilities, clinical utility, and integration into prenatal healthcare. Relevant peer-reviewed literature published between 2015 and 2025 was identified through searches of PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The reviewed literature indicates that wearable devices show promise for monitoring maternal activity, sleep, and cardiovascular parameters, while emerging systems aim to assess fetal heart rate, movement, and uterine activity. However, variability in data accuracy, limited clinical validation, privacy concerns, and user acceptance challenges continue to constrain widespread implementation. Further large-scale, methodologically robust studies and standardized regulatory frameworks are needed to support the safe and effective integration of wearable technologies into routine prenatal care.

Keywords

artificial intelligence, digital health, maternal health, mHealth, pregnancy monitoring, prenatal care, wearable sensors

Introduction

Maternal health during pregnancy is a key determinant of both individual and population health outcomes (Zar et al. 2019). Despite substantial advances in ob-

stetric care, maternal morbidity and mortality remain major global challenges, with an estimated 287,000 maternal deaths reported worldwide in 2020, most resulting from preventable pregnancy-related complications (WHO 2023). These figures underscore the need

for improved strategies to monitor maternal and fetal well-being throughout gestation.

Maternal health during pregnancy is essential from a demographic, clinical, and economic perspective (Moran et al. 2020). From a demographic standpoint, the health of pregnant women and newborns serves as a critical indicator of a population's overall well-being (Zar et al. 2019). Clinically, the ability to continuously monitor key physiological parameters during pregnancy holds substantial potential for improving maternal–fetal outcomes. Economically, the integration of wearable health technologies may contribute to more efficient use of healthcare resources by enabling early detection of complications and reducing the burden on clinical services (Gentili et al. 2022; De Sario Velasquez et al. 2024a).

Conventional prenatal care relies primarily on scheduled clinical visits and episodic assessments (Kriebs 2010). While effective for many pregnancies, this approach may fail to capture dynamic physiological changes or provide early warning of emerging complications, particularly in low-resource or geographically remote settings (Feig et al. 2017; Burk et al. 2025). As a result, continuous monitoring strategies have gained attention as a means of improving early detection and supporting more personalized prenatal care.

In response to these limitations, the rapid advancement of wearable health technologies offers a promising opportunity to enhance prenatal monitoring. Wearable devices, including smartwatches, fitness trackers, and specialized biosensors, enable continuous, noninvasive, and personalized monitoring of vital parameters (Huhn et al. 2022). When integrated with mobile health (mHealth) applications and artificial intelligence (AI), these technologies support real-time data collection, early identification of abnormalities, and closer engagement between pregnant women and healthcare providers (Liu et al. 2024). Their adoption in pregnancy care has increased substantially in recent years, supported by clinical studies and systematic reviews that highlight their potential to enhance prenatal outcomes (Alim and Imtiaz 2023; Maugeri et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2024).

Current evidence suggests that wearable technologies may offer meaningful benefits for the early identification of pregnancy-related complications and for improving the continuity of prenatal care (Runkle et al. 2019; Keebler Bruce et al. 2024; Mohamed et al. 2025). However, the clinical utility of these devices remains influenced by several challenges, including variability in data accuracy and reliability (Liu et al. 2024), concerns related to data privacy and security, and differences in user acceptance and satisfaction (Sifaoui and Eastin 2024).

Against this background, the present narrative review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of wearable health-tracking technologies used during pregnancy, with a particular focus on their monitoring capabilities, clinical applications, and integration into prenatal care. By synthesizing evidence from the past decade, this review seeks to clarify the current role of wearable technologies in prenatal health monitoring, identify ongoing challenges, and highlight directions for future research and clinical implementation.

Materials and methods

Review design

This article was prepared as a narrative review aiming to summarize and critically discuss current evidence on wearable health-tracking technologies used during pregnancy. A narrative approach was selected to allow flexibility in synthesizing diverse study designs, technological platforms, and clinical applications within this rapidly evolving research area (Greenhalgh et al. 2016).

Literature search strategy

A structured literature search was conducted to identify relevant peer-reviewed publications. The following electronic databases were searched: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search covered articles published between January 2015 and June 2025, a period characterized by significant advancements in wearable and digital health technologies.

Search terms included combinations of keywords related to pregnancy and digital health technologies, such as wearable devices, wearable sensors, mobile health, mHealth, digital health, pregnancy monitoring, prenatal care, maternal health, fetal monitoring, gestational tracking, and artificial intelligence. Reference lists of relevant review articles were also manually screened to identify additional pertinent studies.

Study selection and inclusion criteria

The eligibility criteria required that studies meet the following conditions:

1. Focus on pregnancy or maternal–fetal health;
2. Incorporate or describe wearable or mobile sensor technology used for monitoring;
3. Provide empirical data, feasibility results, or clinical outcomes;
4. Be published in English between January 2015 and June 2025.

Exclusion criteria included editorials, commentaries, patents, non-health consumer gadget marketing materials, and studies lacking methodological clarity.

This narrative review did not adhere to a formal PRISMA meta-analysis framework; however, the steps outlined above were implemented to improve scientific transparency. The included studies were thematically categorized into maternal monitoring, fetal monitoring, mHealth applications, artificial intelligence integration, and user acceptance and were synthesized narratively due to substantial variation in device types, outcomes, and target populations.

Data extraction and synthesis

Data relevant to the selected studies were retrieved and summarized narratively. Extracted information included the type of wearable technology, monitored physiological

parameters, intended clinical application, and key findings related to pregnancy care. Due to heterogeneity in study design, outcomes, and technologies, the findings were synthesized thematically rather than quantitatively.

The narrative synthesis focused on major thematic areas, including types of wearable technologies, monitored maternal and fetal parameters, clinical applications, user perspectives, and challenges related to data accuracy, privacy, and implementation in prenatal care settings.

Methodological considerations

As this was a narrative review, no formal risk-of-bias assessment or quantitative meta-analysis was performed. However, emphasis was placed on including studies with clear methodology, relevance to pregnancy monitoring, and scientific credibility. The narrative approach allowed contextual interpretation of findings and facilitated the identification of research gaps in the field of wearable health technologies during pregnancy.

Results and discussion

The available literature describes a progressive evolution of wearable health-tracking technologies, with increasing relevance for prenatal care applications. The development of wearable health-tracking devices began gaining momentum in the early 2000s. Initial models primarily consisted of pedometers and fitness bands designed to track physical activity, including step count and calorie expenditure (Shei et al. 2022). Over time, as technologies evolved, additional features were incorporated, including heart rate monitoring, sleep tracking, and stress level assessment (Smuck et al. 2021).

The application of wearable technologies in pregnancy care has expanded considerably with the introduction

of specialized devices and mobile health applications capable of tracking a broader range of parameters, as summarized in Table 1 (Alim and Imtiaz 2023). Table 1 highlights representative peer-reviewed studies illustrating the range of wearable technologies and applications discussed in the literature. Reported applications include fetal heart rate, fetal movement, uterine contractions, and other pregnancy-specific physiological indicators (Liu et al. 2024). Some applications also provide educational content to support expectant mothers in understanding developmental changes occurring throughout gestation (Mhajna et al. 2022; Maugeri et al. 2023; Ratanasak et al. 2025). This evolution has significantly enhanced the potential for telemedicine consultations and remote prenatal monitoring.

The progression of these technologies has been both substantial and steady, positioning wearable devices as valuable tools in modern obstetric care. However, their widespread adoption requires ongoing scientific evaluation and appropriate regulatory oversight to ensure safety, reliability, and clinical efficacy.

Types of wearable health technologies used in pregnancy

The literature describes wearable health-tracking devices used during pregnancy as serving multiple roles, ranging from monitoring maternal activity, heart rate, sleep, and weight to specialized functions such as detecting fetal heart rate, movement, and uterine activity. These technologies may also enable early detection of infections, provide personalized recommendations, and enhance patient-provider communication through real-time data sharing. Collectively, these functions support continuous, individualized, and responsive prenatal care (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Functions of wearable health-tracking devices during pregnancy. These technologies monitor maternal parameters (activity, heart rate, sleep, and weight) and pregnancy-specific indicators (fetal heart rate, movement, and uterine activity), while also facilitating early detection of infections, personalized care, and improved communication between patients and healthcare providers.

Table 1. Selected peer-reviewed studies on wearable health technologies in pregnancy (2015–2025).

Reference	Device/technology	Study design	Pregnancy focus	Key findings
Walter et al. 2022 (Walter et al. 2022)	Wireless wearable sensors (sleep monitoring)	Observational cohort	Sleep-disordered breathing	Wearable sleep sensors identified sleep-disordered breathing patterns associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes
Liu et al. 2024 (Liu et al. 2024)	Multisensor wearable platforms integrated with artificial intelligence	Narrative review	Pregnancy monitoring	Review findings suggest that AI-enhanced wearables may improve data interpretation; however, further clinical validation is required
Runkle et al. 2019 (Runkle et al. 2019)	Wearable environmental and health sensors	Mixed-methods	Maternal monitoring	Patients and healthcare providers reported generally high usability, alongside concerns regarding data accuracy
Dunn et al. 2018 (Dunn et al. 2018)	Consumer and clinical wearable devices	Narrative review	Medical applications	Narrative review describing the emerging role of wearable technologies in clinical and preventive healthcare
Li et al. 2021 (Li et al. 2021)	Mobile health (mHealth) applications and wearable-linked platforms	Qualitative interview study	Pregnancy care	Qualitative analysis showed generally positive user perceptions, influenced by perceived accuracy and reliability
Bjelica et al. 2020 (Bjelica et al. 2020)	Integrated digital ecosystem using wearable and pervasive technologies	Systems design and framework proposal	Pregnancy care management	Proposed an integrated digital ecosystem for pregnancy care management using pervasive technologies
Raab et al. 2023 (Raab et al. 2023)	Wearable devices integrated with mobile applications	Scoping review	Gestational weight gain (GWG), GDM prevention	Scoping review indicating that app-supported digital interventions are associated with improved management of gestational weight gain and metabolic risk
Karim et al. 2024 (Karim et al. 2024)	Person-generated health data platforms incorporating wearable devices	Scoping review	Women's health	Scoping review highlighting the potential of person-generated health data to support personalized and patient-centered care
Maugeri et al. 2023 (Maugeri et al. 2023)	Wearable sensor technologies for maternal and fetal monitoring	Scoping review	Foetal and pregnancy outcomes	Scoping review demonstrating that wearable sensors facilitate longitudinal data collection in pregnancy and fetal outcome research
Babu and Snyder 2023 (Babu and Snyder 2023)	Integration of wearable devices with multi-omics profiling approaches	Narrative review	General health, including pregnancy	Narrative review discussing the integration of multi-omics data and wearable technologies for personalized health monitoring
Ming et al. 2023 (Ming et al. 2024)	Digital health tools, including wearable sensors and mobile platforms	Narrative review	Maternal, fetal, and neonatal infection management	Review describing the role of digital health innovations in supporting maternal, fetal, and neonatal infection monitoring and management
Malloy 2024 (Malloy 2024)	Digital health interventions incorporating mobile and wearable technologies	Narrative review	Birth equity	Review examining the potential of digital health interventions to address disparities and support birth equity
Alim and Imtiaz 2023 (Alim and Imtiaz 2023)	Wearable sensor technologies for maternal health monitoring	Systematic review	Maternal health	Systematic review identifying key strengths, limitations, and gaps in wearable sensor technologies for maternal health monitoring
Hossain et al. 2023 (Hossain et al. 2023)	Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled wearable platforms	Systematic review	Pregnancy care coordination	Systematic review suggesting that IoT-based systems may improve pregnancy care coordination and monitoring, while highlighting interoperability challenges
Marin et al. 2019 (Marin et al. 2019)	Smart wristband prototype	Feasibility study	Preeclampsia risk	Longitudinal wearable data reflected physiological changes corresponding to hormonal shifts across pregnancy
Unnamed cohort study, 2025	Consumer wearable devices (Apple, Garmin, Fitbit)	Longitudinal observational cohort	Pregnancy physiological changes	Longitudinal data aligned with hormonal and physiological shifts
Keeler Bruce et al. 2024 (Keeler Bruce et al. 2024)	Oura Ring	Longitudinal cohort	Pregnancy trajectories	Wearable biometrics captured physiological changes across gestation
NCT05709327 (Ongoing trial) (Clinicaltrials.gov 2025)	Smart ring integrated with a smartphone-based monitoring platform	Ongoing prospective feasibility study	Pregnancy health monitoring	Evaluates feasibility, compliance, and acceptability in diverse populations
Apple AI model study, 2025 (Majahan 2025)	Apple Watch data analyzed using an artificial intelligence-based behavioral model	Retrospective model development and validation study	Pregnancy detection	Exploratory analysis reporting approximately 92% accuracy in pregnancy detection using wearable-derived behavioral data

Abbreviations: GDM – gestational diabetes mellitus; GWG – gestational weight gain; IoT – internet of things; AI – artificial intelligence.

Note: Study design classifications are based on the primary methodological approach described by the authors. Some entries reflect emerging or exploratory evidence and are included to illustrate technological trends rather than established clinical validation.

Wearable sensors

Wearable health-tracking devices incorporate multiple embedded components, known as wearable sensors (Runkle et al. 2019; Alim and Imtiaz 2023; Liu et al. 2024).

These sensors may be integrated into wearable technologies or applied independently to the body. Their primary role is to collect physiological data, which are then processed—often with the assistance of artificial intelligence (AI)—to derive clinically relevant insights. AI enhances

the interpretation of sensor data by identifying patterns, detecting anomalies, and facilitating personalized diagnostics (Shajari et al. 2023).

Wearable sensors are generally categorized into five main groups and are often used in combination to provide a comprehensive assessment of maternal and fetal health:

- **Biopotential sensors:** These sensors detect electrical activity associated with physiological processes such as maternal and fetal heart rate. They enable high-precision analysis of vital parameters and encompass modalities such as electrocardiography (ECG), electroencephalography (EEG), and electrohysterography (EHG) (Qureshi and Krishnan 2018; Seshadri et al. 2019; Palumbo et al. 2020, 2021). Examples include flexible sensors placed on the maternal abdomen and chest, as well as home-use wearable devices based on electrodes positioned near the navel (Alim and Imtiaz 2023). These sensors convert biological interactions into electrical signals, a process facilitated by recognition elements—such as enzymes or antibodies—fixed on their surface. The accuracy of these biosensors depends on the stability of biological components and the efficiency of signal conversion. Studies report heart rate detection accuracies ranging from 87.6% to 95.8% (Chhabra and Madaan 2023; Spicher et al. 2025). Data processing algorithms are commonly applied to distinguish between maternal and fetal signals, enabling early detection of fetal complications, such as hypoxia or cardiac abnormalities.
- **Pressure and inertial sensors:** These sensors detect fetal movement and uterine contractions, providing valuable information for pregnancy monitoring (Liu et al. 2024). Multipoint sensor systems, such as devices incorporating three sensors mounted on an elastic structure or passive belts equipped with motion detectors, are commonly used to monitor abdominal motion.
- **Acoustic sensors:** These sensors use sound wave detection to monitor fetal heart rate, offering a noninvasive method for cardiac assessment.
- **Electrodermal sensors:** These sensors measure changes in skin conductance to assess maternal stress levels and emotional states.
- **Multimodal systems:** These platforms integrate multiple sensor types to provide a holistic view of maternal and fetal health.

Wearable devices are designed primarily for maternal monitoring, measuring key parameters such as heart rate, respiratory rate, physical activity, blood pressure, and sleep quality. Data acquisition is typically performed using wristbands, rings, or photoplethysmographic (PPG) sensors. More advanced multimodal systems combine multiple sensors to measure both maternal and fetal variables simultaneously, allowing concurrent monitoring of both.

Maternal physical activity can be categorized into at least ten everyday activities—such as walking, cooking, and exercising—captured through movement analysis. A strong

correlation has been observed between wearable-derived activity data and measurements obtained through conventional medical devices, reinforcing the reliability of wearable systems in prenatal care (Kominiarek et al. 2019).

Following the collection of sensor-derived measurements, data undergo systematic processing. In the case of acoustic sensors, signal quality is improved through the use of specialized filtering techniques that eliminate background noise, such as electrical interference from power lines, and reduce artifacts caused by body motion. The analysis targets physical parameters, including the duration, intensity, and position of fetal movements. Clinical evaluations of these technologies have reported fetal motion detection accuracies of up to 90% (Rattanasak et al. 2025; Spicher et al. 2025).

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays an increasingly vital role in the interpretation of sensor-acquired data (Shajari et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2024; Ghadi et al. 2025). AI-based algorithms are increasingly explored to identify potential complications, support diagnostic processes, and inform clinical decision-making. These systems can evaluate fetal movement patterns, predict uterine contractions, and detect early signs of pregnancy-related conditions such as preeclampsia. Integration with mobile applications and cloud platforms further enhances system effectiveness by enabling real-time analysis, remote monitoring, and centralized storage of health data. Most applications remain in developmental or early validation stages.

Mobile applications and platforms in pregnancy monitoring

mHealth applications and platforms offer pregnant women accessible and user-centered environments for tracking fetal development and promoting maternal well-being. These tools provide personalized health advice, track vital parameters, and offer educational resources throughout pregnancy (Hossain et al. 2023; Raab et al. 2023; Clinicaltrials.gov 2025). Their usefulness is particularly evident in remote or underserved areas, where access to prenatal healthcare services is often limited.

A significant proportion of women begin pregnancy with pre-existing overweight or obesity, which substantially increases the risk of excessive gestational weight gain (GWG) and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). Both conditions are associated with adverse outcomes, including postpartum weight retention, development of type 2 diabetes, fetal macrosomia, and an increased risk of childhood obesity.

Digital lifestyle interventions are described as practical and scalable approaches to mitigate these risks. mHealth and eHealth solutions provide cost-effective and accessible support for behavior modification, health education, and self-monitoring. Commonly reported features across mHealth platforms include:

- Weight, nutrition, and activity tracking
- Goal setting and progress monitoring
- Educational content

- Gamification elements to increase motivation
- Social connectivity for peer support
- Mental health and emotional wellness tools

Most interventions focus on promoting balanced nutrition and physical activity; however, they increasingly integrate psychological and behavioral health components to support holistic maternal care.

Wearable health technologies also play an increasingly important role in the detection and management of infections in pregnant individuals, fetuses, and neonates, particularly in resource-limited settings. Maternal and neonatal infections remain among the leading causes of preventable mortality, especially in low- and middle-income countries (WHO 2023; Regan et al. 2025). The impact of these infections is exacerbated by poor hygiene conditions, limited access to clean water, restricted availability of antibiotics, and the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance.

Through their accessibility and scalability, digital health technologies can enhance the diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of infections. Telemedicine platforms improve access to care in geographically remote areas (Tsou et al. 2021). At the same time, electronic health applications enable continuous collection of maternal and fetal data, thereby improving diagnostic accuracy and supporting individualized treatment planning.

Wearable devices and biosensors are beneficial for monitoring vital signs in both the mother and fetus. In fetal applications, these technologies can support early detection of clinical deterioration, facilitating timely interventions that may reduce morbidity and mortality. Continuous, noninvasive tracking of physiological parameters, such as heart rate, temperature, and respiratory rate, provides clinicians with valuable real-time information—especially critical when conventional diagnostic tools are limited in capability.

Implications of mobile health beyond pregnancy

Although this review focuses on pregnancy, several studies place wearable and mobile health technologies within the broader context of women's health. Mobile health technologies have expanded beyond pregnancy monitoring to support the overall health and well-being of women across various life stages. Patient-generated health data—data collected outside traditional clinical settings through mobile applications, wearable devices, and web-based technologies—has emerged as a transformative tool in women's health management.

Patient-generated health data enables personalized, continuous, and accessible health monitoring, providing women with greater autonomy and engagement in managing their health. These data sources have been shown to enhance early detection of health changes, promote proactive care-seeking behaviors, and facilitate more precise clinical decision-making.

By integrating patient-generated health data (PGHD) into clinical workflows and health systems, healthcare providers can deliver more comprehensive, patient-centered care, particularly in underserved and remote populations.

Mobile and digital health interventions are widely used across multiple health domains relevant to women's well-being. These include:

- Pregnancy and postpartum care
- General preventive health and self-care
- Physical activity and nutrition
- Blood glucose monitoring
- Cancer screening and follow-up
- Cardiometabolic health
- Mental health and psychological support
- Menstrual, sexual, and reproductive health
- Diabetes management
- Osteoporosis prevention
- Cardiovascular disease monitoring
- Chronic condition management

Among these applications, menstrual cycle tracking and fertility monitoring remain two of the most prevalent use cases in women's digital health tools.

Technology platforms utilized

The most common technologies used for collecting and managing patient-generated health data (PGHD) in women's health include:

- Mobile applications (the most widely adopted tool for self-monitoring and education)
- Wearable devices, such as smartwatches and fitness bands
- Web platforms and patient portals
- Smart home health devices (e.g., smart scales and smart thermometers)
- Other connected digital health tools

User perspectives and adoption factors

Findings from recent studies (Li et al. 2021; Jacob et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2022; Honglin et al. 2024) suggest that users evaluate and adopt mobile health solutions based on several interrelated factors:

- Design and functionality: Personalization options, reminders and notifications, intuitive user interfaces, and interoperability with other applications are considered essential features that impact user engagement and satisfaction.
- Accuracy and reliability: The credibility of mobile health technologies depends heavily on the accuracy of data collection, robustness of embedded algorithms, and inclusion of culturally relevant features. A lack of culturally adapted content may serve as a barrier to adoption in diverse populations.

- Target audience and acceptance: Successful implementation of digital health solutions depends on tailoring interventions to different age groups, linguistic backgrounds, and cultural contexts. User acceptance is significantly enhanced when the technology is recommended by a healthcare provider, underscoring the value of clinician endorsement in fostering trust and promoting long-term use.

Personalized care in digital health

Personalized care represents a cornerstone in the successful implementation of digital tools in healthcare. It is based on the ability of technologies to tailor their functions to individual user needs, preferences, and health status. Through technological integration, personalized care becomes more accessible and practical, offering enhanced support to both maternal and fetal well-being during pregnancy (Syed-Abdul et al. 2020).

Research indicates that both patients and healthcare professionals respond positively to the integration of wearable devices and mobile health (mHealth) technologies into healthcare systems. These technologies have the potential to enhance communication and collaboration between patients and providers, thereby facilitating effective management of maternal health (Ullah et al. 2024; Brückner et al. 2025). Furthermore, they offer a cost-effective solution for the remote monitoring of both low-risk pregnancies and pregnancies requiring closer surveillance (De Sario Velasquez et al. 2024b; Mohamed et al. 2025).

Critical evaluation of evidence

The current evidence is influenced by multiple biases, including studies supported by industry for device development, selection bias favoring technologically adept patient groups, and underrepresentation of low-resource populations. Moreover, the majority of feasibility studies fail to address maternal concerns, technology weariness, or the potential for false reassurance—elements that could adversely affect health-seeking behaviors. Consequently, available data must be evaluated judiciously, and future studies should integrate psychological outcomes, cost-effectiveness evaluations, and health equity assessments.

Regulatory and ethical considerations

A significant constraint in the current digital maternal health landscape is the lack of unified regulatory oversight. In the European Union, medical-grade pregnancy monitoring devices are governed by Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on Medical Devices (MDR), which requires clinical evaluation, CE marking, and evidence of safety and performance (EU 2017). In contrast, many commercially available wearables (e.g., smartwatches, fitness bands) are marketed as lifestyle or wellness products and do not undergo medical device approval. This inconsistency generates uncertainty for healthcare professionals regarding safety, liability, and

appropriate clinical application. In the United States, the FDA differentiates between wellness technologies and approved medical-grade digital systems, resulting in most consumer devices being exempt from regulatory oversight. Data privacy risks are particularly relevant during pregnancy, as biometric data may include reproductive and geographical information. Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) in the U.S.A. requires secure data storage, encryption, user consent for data sharing, and transparent information regarding third-party data access. Integrating ethics into prenatal care therefore necessitates robust institutional governance and clearly defined clinical standards.

Clinical outcomes of wearable technologies during pregnancy

Despite the rapid integration of wearable devices into prenatal care, clinical evidence demonstrating quantifiable maternal and neonatal outcomes remains limited. A small number of randomized and prospective studies have reported potential benefits. Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) in pregnancies complicated by diabetes has been associated with improved time-in-range metrics, reduced rates of neonatal hypoglycemia, and fewer admissions to neonatal intensive care units (NICU) compared with self-monitoring alone (Feig et al. 2017; Burk et al. 2025). Longitudinal physiology-based monitoring using smart rings and smartwatches has demonstrated the ability to identify early deviations in heart rate variability and sleep patterns prior to symptom manifestation (Keeler Bruce et al. 2024). On this basis, early identification may facilitate the prompt detection of conditions such as preeclampsia, infection, or metabolic dysregulation.

Nonetheless, large-scale studies validating fetal heart rate monitors, uterine contraction detectors, and fetal movement trackers remain limited. Many devices demonstrate high sensitivity in controlled laboratory environments; however, their accuracy decreases in women with elevated body mass index, multiple gestations, or during periods of intense physical activity. Thus, most existing evidence emphasizes feasibility, user satisfaction, and technological promise rather than demonstrable improvements in clinical outcomes, underscoring the need for multicenter clinical trials with standardized endpoints.

The role of the clinical pharmacist in digital prenatal care

Currently, a distinct paradigm change is occurring, as pharmacists are increasingly transitioning from prescription dispensers to healthcare advisors, a shift that necessitates access to clear physiological information gathered via wearable devices to fulfill this role. The incorporation of wearable monitoring technologies strongly aligns with the development of pharmaceutical care models that emphasize prevention, adherence, and individualized therapy, especially in high-risk patients such as pregnant women. Clinical pharmacists

can assist in evaluating medication-related risk indicators identified through physiological data obtained from wearables (e.g., tachycardia following β -agonist exposure, glucose fluctuations in gestational diabetes management).

Subsequent essential pharmaceutical care interventions may be enhanced by information harvested from wearable devices, including:

- Instructing expectant patients on the safe use of technology and appropriate interpretation of device outputs;
- Recognizing potential drug–disease interactions or medication-induced physiological alterations;
- Participating in interdisciplinary remote monitoring initiatives and prioritizing aberrant data alerts.

Consequently, digital maternal monitoring provides an avenue for strengthening pharmacist-led public healthcare, particularly in settings with limited obstetric resources.

Challenges and limitations

Across the reviewed literature, several challenges are consistently identified. One of the primary concerns relates to data accuracy. Not all wearable devices deliver clinically reliable measurements, and inaccurate data may result in misguided clinical decisions, potentially affecting maternal and fetal outcomes. Another major challenge involves data security and privacy. The sensitive nature of health-related information requires robust safeguards to prevent unauthorized access or data breaches. User variability presents an additional layer of complexity, as physiological and behavioral differences between individuals can influence the accuracy and applicability of data-driven insights.

Other limitations include cost and accessibility barriers, varying levels of digital literacy, lack of standardization across devices and platforms, and infrastructural disparities, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

Conclusion

Wearable health-tracking devices have emerged as vital tools in contemporary prenatal care, offering innovative solutions for monitoring and managing the health of expectant mothers and their developing fetuses. Their primary roles include continuous monitoring of key physiological parameters, detection of specific symptoms, enhancement of patient engagement and awareness, and improved communication between patients and healthcare providers.

These technologies contribute to more accessible, personalized, and accurate healthcare delivery. However, their implementation also presents distinct challenges, including concerns related to data accuracy, information security, and effective integration with conventional clinical practice.

To maximize the effectiveness and long-term impact of wearable technologies in pregnancy care, continued investment is required in the development of high-precision sensors and real-time data interpretation algorithms that

ensure robust and clinically reliable information. Establishing standardized protocols and regulatory frameworks for data privacy and third-party data use is essential to build user trust and ensure ethical application. Furthermore, large-scale clinical studies involving diverse populations are necessary to validate device efficacy and support evidence-based implementation. Equally important is user education and empowerment, which plays a critical role in achieving optimal outcomes through informed engagement with digital health tools. Digital monitoring should augment, rather than replace, traditional prenatal care and will achieve its full clinical effectiveness only when integrated with multidisciplinary oversight, including clinical pharmacists, obstetricians, and digital health specialists.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This project is funded by the European Union NextGenerationEU procedure "Creating a network of research universities" from the National Plan for Recovery and Resilience, project "Research University–Medical University–Pleven," contract #BG-RRP-2.004-0003-C01.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Afiyze Ahmedova <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2241-4908>

Nadia Veleva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1027-5951>

Svetoslav Stoev <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6165-5674>

Elina Petkova-Gueorguieva <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1488-3863>

Vesselina Yanachkova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4205-7502>

Hristina Lebanova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4835-6965>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Alim A, Intiaz MH (2023) Wearable Sensors for the Monitoring of Maternal Health-A Systematic Review. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 23: 2411. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23052411>
- Babu M, Snyder M (2023) Multi-Omics Profiling for Health. *Molecular & cellular proteomics: MCP* 22: 100561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100561>
- Bjelica D, Bjelica A, Despotović-Zrakić M, Radenković B, Barać D, Dogatović M (2020) Designing an IT Ecosystem for Pregnancy Care Management Based on Pervasive Technologies. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)* 9: 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9010012>
- Brückner S, Sadare O, Fesl S, Scheibe M, Lang C, Gilbert S (2025) Attitudes of healthcare professionals and researchers toward wearable and app derived patient generated health data. *npj Digital Medicine* 8: 186. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01568-4>
- Burk J, Ross GP, Hernandez TL, Colagiuri S, Sweeting A (2025) Evidence for improved glucose metrics and perinatal outcomes with continuous glucose monitoring compared to self-monitoring in diabetes during pregnancy. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology* 233: 162–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2025.04.010>
- Chhabra P, Madaan R (2023) Atrial fibrillation detection through ML approach: A comparative study. *Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology* 44: 3389–3401. <https://doi.org/10.52783/tjpt.v44.i4.1475>
- Clinicaltrials.gov (2025) Integrating smart ring wearable technology in pregnancy health monitoring (I-SMART). *clinicaltrials.gov*. Clinical trial registration. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT05709327> [September 1, 2025]
- De Sario Velasquez GD, Borna S, Maniaci MJ, Coffey JD, Haider CR, Demaerschalk BM, Forte AJ (2024a) Economic perspective of the use of wearables in health care: A systematic review. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings: Digital Health* 2: 299–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpdig.2024.05.003>
- De Sario Velasquez GD, Borna S, Maniaci MJ, Coffey JD, Haider CR, Demaerschalk BM, Forte AJ (2024b) Economic perspective of the use of wearables in health care: A systematic review. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings: Digital Health* 2: 299–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpdig.2024.05.003>
- Dunn J, Runge R, Snyder M (2018) Wearables and the medical revolution. *Personalized Medicine* 15: 429–448. <https://doi.org/10.2217/pme-2018-0044>
- EU (2017) Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj/eng> [January 4, 2026]
- Feig DS, Donovan LE, Corcoy R, Murphy KE, Amiel SA, Hunt KF, Asztalos E, Barrett JFR, Sanchez JJ, De Leiva A, Hod M, Jovanovic L, Keely E, McManus R, Hutton EK, Meek CL, Stewart ZA, Wysocki T, O'Brien R, Ruedy K, Kollman C, Tomlinson G, Murphy HR, Grisoni J, Byrne C, Davenport K, Neoh S, Gougeon C, Oldford C, Young C, Green L, Rossi B, Rogers H, Cleave B, Strom M, Adelantado JM, Isabel Chico A, Tundidor D, Malcolm J, Henry K, Morris D, Rayman G, Fowler D, Mitchell S, Rosier J, Temple R, Turner J, Canciani G, Hewapathirana N, Piper L, Kudirka A, Watson M, Bonomo M, Pintauro B, Bertuzzi F, Daniela G, Mion E, Lowe J, Halperin I, Rogowsky A, Adib S, Lindsay R, Carty D, Crawford I, Mackenzie F, McSorley T, Booth J, McInnes N, Smith A, Stanton I, Tazzeo T, Weisnagel J, Mansell P, Jones N, Babington G, Spick D, MacDougall M, Chilton S, Cutts T, Perkins M, Scott E, Endersby D, Dover A, Dougherty F, Johnston S, Heller S, Novodorsky P, Hudson S, Nisbet C, Ransom T, Coolen J, Baxendale D, Holt R, Forbes J, Martin N, Walbridge F, Dunne F, Conway S, Egan A, Kirwin C, Maresh M, Kearney G, Morris J, Quinn S, Bilous R, Mukhtar R, Godbout A, Daigle S, Lubina A, Jackson M, Paul E, Taylor J, Houlden R, Breen A, Banerjee A, Brackenridge A, Briley A, Reid A, Singh C, Newstead-Angel J, Baxter J, Philip S, Chlost M, Murray L, Castorino K, Frase D, Lou O, Pragnell M (2017) Continuous glucose monitoring in pregnant women with type 1 diabetes (CONCEPTT): a multicentre international randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet* 390: 2347–2359. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32400-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32400-5)
- Gentili A, Failla G, Melnyk A, Puleo V, Tanna GLD, Ricciardi W, Cascini F (2022) The cost-effectiveness of digital health interventions: A systematic review of the literature. *Frontiers in Public Health* 10: 787135. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.787135>
- Ghadi YY, Shah SFA, Waheed W, Mazhar T, Ahmad W, Saeed MM, Hamam H (2025) Integration of wearable technology and artificial intelligence in digital health for remote patient care. *Journal of Cloud Computing* 14: 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13677-025-00759-4>
- Greenhalgh T, Raftery J, Hanney S, Glover M (2016) Research impact: a narrative review. *BMC Medicine* 14: 78. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-016-0620-8>
- Honglin D, Jianghua Z, Hui C (2024) Quality factors affecting the continued use of mobile health apps in ethnic minority regions of Southwest China using PLS-SEM and ANN. *Scientific Reports* 14: 25469. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-75410-4>
- Hossain MM, Kashem MA, Islam MM, Sahidullah M, Mumu SH, Uddin J, Aray DG, de la Torre Diez I, Ashraf I, Samad MA (2023) Internet of Things in Pregnancy Care Coordination and Management: A Systematic Review. *Sensors* 23: 9367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23239367>
- Huhn S, Axt M, Gunga H-C, Maggioni MA, Munga S, Obor D, Sié A, Boudo V, Bunker A, Sauerborn R, Bärnighausen T, Barteit S (2022) The Impact of Wearable Technologies in Health Research: Scoping Review. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth* 10: e34384. <https://doi.org/10.2196/34384>
- Jacob C, Sezgin E, Sanchez-Vazquez A, Ivory C (2022) Sociotechnical Factors Affecting Patients' Adoption of Mobile Health Tools: Systematic Literature Review and Narrative Synthesis. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth* 10: e36284. <https://doi.org/10.2196/36284>
- Karim JL, Wan R, Tabet RS, Chiu DS, Talhouk A (2024) Person-generated health data in women's health: Scoping review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26: e53327. <https://doi.org/10.2196/53327>
- Keeler Bruce L, González D, Dasgupta S, Smarr BL (2024) Biometrics of complete human pregnancy recorded by wearable devices. *npj Digital Medicine* 7: 207. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01183-9>
- Kominiarek MA, Balmert LC, Tolo H, Grobman W, Simon M (2019) A feasibility study of activity tracking devices in pregnancy. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 19: 401. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2557-3>
- Kriebs JM (2010) Guidelines for Perinatal Care. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health* 55: e37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmwh.2009.12.013>
- Li J, Silvera-Tawil D, Varnfield M, Hussain MS, Math V (2021) Users' perceptions toward mHealth technologies for health and well-being monitoring in pregnancy care: Qualitative interview study. *JMIR formative research* 5: e28628. <https://doi.org/10.2196/28628>
- Liu L, Pu Y, Fan J, Yan Y, Liu W, Luo K, Wang Y, Zhao G, Chen T, Puiui PD, Huang H (2024) Wearable sensors, data processing, and artificial

- intelligence in pregnancy monitoring: A review. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 24: 6426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24196426>
- Liu Y, Lu X, Li C, Zhao G (2022) The influence of content presentation on users' intention to adopt mhealth applications: Based on the S-O-R theoretical model. *Sustainability* 14: 9900. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14169900>
- Majahan R (2025) Apple's Wearable AI Detects Pregnancy With Over 90% Accuracy. *BigRio*. <https://bigr.io/apples-wearable-ai-detects-pregnancy-with-over-90-accuracy/> [September 1, 2025]
- Malloy S (2024) Impact of digital health interventions on birth equity: A review. *Seminars in Reproductive Medicine* 42: 140–150. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0044-1791206>
- Marin I, Goga N, Vasilateanu A, Gradinaru A, Racovita V (2019) Smart Solution for the Detection of Preeclampsia. In: 2019 E-Health and Bioengineering Conference (EHB), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EHB47216.2019.8969948>
- Maugeri A, Barchitta M, Agodi A (2023) How wearable sensors can support the research on foetal and pregnancy outcomes: A scoping review. *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 13: 218. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm13020218>
- Mhajna M, Sadeh B, Yagel S, Sohn C, Schwartz N, Warsof S, Zahar Y, Reches A (2022) A novel, cardiac-derived algorithm for uterine activity monitoring in a wearable remote device. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 10: 933612. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2022.933612>
- Ming DK, Merriel A, Freeman DME, Kingdon C, Chimwaza Y, Islam MS, Cass A, Greenfield B, Malata A, Hoque M, Saha S, Holmes AH (2024) Advancing the management of maternal, fetal, and neonatal infection through harnessing digital health innovations. *The Lancet. Digital Health* 6: e926–e933. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(24\)00217-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(24)00217-6)
- Mohamed H, Ismail A, Sutan R, Rahman RA, Juval K (2025) A scoping review of digital technologies in antenatal care: recent progress and applications of digital technologies. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 25: 153. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-025-07209-8>
- Moran PS, Wuytack F, Turner M, Normand C, Brown S, Begley C, Daly D (2020) Economic burden of maternal morbidity – A systematic review of cost-of-illness studies. *PLoS ONE* 15: e0227377. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0227377>
- Palumbo A, Vizza P, Calabrese B, Ielpo N (2021) Biopotential signal monitoring systems in rehabilitation: A review. *Sensors* 21: 7172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21217172>
- Palumbo A, Calabrese B, Ielpo N, Demeco A, Ammendolia A, Corchiola D (2020) Cloud-based biomedical system for remote monitoring of ALS patients. In: 2020 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), 1469–1476. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BIBM49941.2020.9313485>
- Qureshi F, Krishnan S (2018) Wearable hardware design for the internet of medical things (IoMT). *Sensors* 18: 3812. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18113812>
- Raab R, Geyer K, Zagar S, Hauner H (2023) App-supported lifestyle interventions in pregnancy to manage gestational weight gain and prevent gestational diabetes: Scoping review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 25: e48853. <https://doi.org/10.2196/48853>
- Rattanasak A, Jumphoo T, Pathonsuwan W, Kokkhunthod K, Orkweha K, Phapatanaburi K, Tongdee P, Nimkuntod P, Uthansakul M, Uthansakul P (2025) An iot-enabled wearable device for fetal movement detection using accelerometer and gyroscope sensors. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 25: 1552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25051552>
- Regan D, Mountford N, Coughlan J (2025) Systematic review of methodological approaches in economic evaluations of maternal and neonatal sepsis interventions in low- and middle-income countries. *BMC Health Services Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-025-13799-y>
- Runkle J, Sugg M, Boase D, Galvin SL, C Coulson C (2019) Use of wearable sensors for pregnancy health and environmental monitoring: Descriptive findings from the perspective of patients and providers. *Digital Health* 5: 2055207619828220. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207619828220>
- Seshadri DR, Li RT, Voos JE, Rowbottom JR, Alfes CM, Zorman CA, Drummond CK (2019) Wearable sensors for monitoring the physiological and biochemical profile of the athlete. *npj Digital Medicine* 2: 72. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0150-9>
- Shajari S, Kuruvinschetti K, Komeili A, Sundararaj U (2023) The emergence of ai-based wearable sensors for digital health technology: A review. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 23: 9498. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23239498>
- Shei R-J, Holder IG, Oumsang AS, Paris BA, Paris HL (2022) Wearable activity trackers—advanced technology or advanced marketing? *European Journal of Applied Physiology* 122: 1975–1990. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-022-04951-1>
- Sifaoui A, Eastin MS (2024) “Whispers from the Wrist”: Wearable health monitoring devices and privacy regulations in the U.S.: The loopholes, the challenges, and the opportunities. *Cryptography* 8: 26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryptography8020026>
- Smuck M, Odonkor CA, Wilt JK, Schmidt N, Swiernik MA (2021) The emerging clinical role of wearables: factors for successful implementation in healthcare. *npj Digital Medicine* 4: 45. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00418-3>
- Spicher L, Bell C, Sienko KH, Huan X (2025) Comparative analysis of machine learning approaches for fetal movement detection with linear acceleration and angular rate signals. *Sensors* 25: 2944. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25092944>
- Syed-Abdul S, Zhu X, Fernandez-Luque L (2020) *Digital Health: Mobile and Wearable Devices for Participatory Health Applications*. Elsevier, 234 pp.
- Tsou C, Robinson S, Boyd J, Jamieson A, Blakeman R, Yeung J, McDonnell J, Waters S, Bosich K, Hendrie D (2021) Effectiveness of telehealth in rural and remote emergency departments: Systematic review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 23: e30632. <https://doi.org/10.2196/30632>
- Ullah MW, Rahman R, Nilima SI, Tasnim AF, Aziz MB (2024) Health behaviors and outcomes of mobile health apps and patient engagement in the USA. *Journal of Computer and Communications* 12: 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jcc.2024.1210007>
- Walter JR, Lee JY, Snoll B, Park JB, Kim DH, Xu S, Barnhart K (2022) Pregnancy outcomes in infertility patients diagnosed with sleep disordered breathing with wireless wearable sensors. *Sleep Medicine* 100: 511–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2022.09.026>
- WHO (2023) Trends in maternal mortality 2000 to 2020: estimates by WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, World Bank Group and UNDESA/Population Division. World Health Organization. [https://www.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=6WnWEAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR17&dq=Trends+in+Maternal+Mortality+2000%E2%80%932020+\(World+Health+Organization+report&ots=93WLIK3rZC&sig=3HhH-f4I-5YsDTI5gcFDIyqtBLc8](https://www.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=6WnWEAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR17&dq=Trends+in+Maternal+Mortality+2000%E2%80%932020+(World+Health+Organization+report&ots=93WLIK3rZC&sig=3HhH-f4I-5YsDTI5gcFDIyqtBLc8) [September 1, 2025]
- Zar HJ, Pellowski JA, Cohen S, Barnett W, Vanker A, Koen N, Stein DJ (2019) Maternal health and birth outcomes in a South African birth cohort study. *PloS One* 14: e0222399. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222399>